

in the sun. The algal flakes from the surface of the plots were collected or scraped and stored. The mean yield of algal flakes per plot was 18–24kg (see table). Differences in the algal yield with various treatment levels were small.

Studies on the cultivation of azolla in rice fields

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New technical measures combined with paired narrow rows were introduced in China in 1973 to encourage year-round cultivation of azolla with rice in paddy fields. By the paired narrow rows technique, azolla propagation could be prolonged without interfering with rice

Yield distribution of rice and azolla in a field where azolla was grown year round. Pucheng, Fukien, China.

Yields (t/ha)		Distribution (%)
<i>Rice</i>		
9.0– 10.0		3.3
10.0– 12.0		25.1
12.0– 13.5		37.4
15.0		34.0
<i>Azolla</i>		
30.0– 31.5		2.3
37.5–112.5		15.9
112.5–150		18.8
150		23.0

growth, ensuring azolla yields several times higher than those in ordinary rice culture.

The rice seedlings are transplanted in double rows. Pairs of rows are spaced 53 to 66 cm apart, with a 13.2-cm spacing between the 2 narrow rows, and a 6.6-cm spacing between hills. Azolla is

then grown in the broad space between pairs of double rows. The closer distance between wider rows (about 50 cm) is suitable for dwarf varieties.

In 1977, this technique was tested at various brigades in Pucheng, Fukien. The average yield of the rice was 6.52 t/ha per crop and the average yield of fresh azolla was 54.5 t/ha per rice crop. The distributions of rice and azolla yield are shown in the table.

In experiments using only harvested azolla as fertilizer in the field (with no added N fertilizer) 9.9 t of rice/ha was harvested from 2 crops grown at 2 sites.

Seventy-five tons of fresh azolla per hectare can supply enough nitrogen for rice yields of 7.5 t/ha.

Successful use of the technique depends on 1) proper spacing of the pairs of rows, 2) proper and sufficient nutrients for both rice and azolla, 3) good water management, and 4) pest control. □

Efficacy of some fungicides against *Trichoconis padwickii*

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The fungus *Trichoconis padwickii* has caused seedling blight, leaf spot, and grain discoloration in many released and pre-release rice varieties in several parts of Mandya, Mysore, and Mercara districts,

Karnataka, since 1976 kharif. To develop a spray schedule, the efficacy of certain fungicides in suppressing spore germination and mycelial growth of the incitant fungus was studied *in vitro*. Eight popular fungicides were tested and found to be effective in the following order: Bavistin, Benlate, Diltzane-M-45, Blitax-50, Difolatan, Hinosan-50, Brassicol, and F. M. Spray.

The systemic fungicide Bavistin was apparently superior to others at all concentrations. At 0.1% strength,

Bavistin completely inhibited spore germination and mycelial growth; Benlate, Dithane M-45, and Blitax-50 gave complete control at 0.2% strength. Hinosan-50 was not superior at 0.05% strength (the dosage usually recommended for blast control) but gave 96–97% inhibition at 0.2% strength. Difolatan, Brassicol, and F. M. Spray at 0.2% strength gave 93–97, 90–94%, and 81–93% inhibition, respectively (see table). □

Efficacy of fungicides in inhibiting the spore germination and mycelial growth of *T. pacwickii*. Kartanaka, India.

Fungicide ^a	Spore						Mycelial growth					
	Germination (%)			Inhibition (%)			Colony diameter (cm)			Inhibition (%)		
	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%
Bavistin 50 W.P.	2.6	0.0	0.0	96.0	100.0	100.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	95	100	100
Benlate, 50 W.P	3.3	0.3	0.0	95.3	99.5	100.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	94	97	100
Dithane M-45	4.6	2.0	0.3	93.0	98.0	99.5	0.2	0.1	0.0	93	97	100
Blitax-50	8.6	3.6	0.6	88.0	95.0	98.5	0.4	0.2	0.0	88	95	100
Hinosan-50	14.0	6.3	2.3	80.0	91.0	97.0	0.9	0.3	0.1	75	91	96
Difolatan	14.3	7.0	2.0	79.5	90.0	97.0	2.2	0.9	0.3	55	82	93
Brassiccol	28.6	12.6	4.3	59.0	82.0	94.0	1.6	0.6	0.2	36	73	90
F.M. Spray	29.6	15.3	4.6	57.7	78.0	93.4	2.5	1.1	0.7	28	70	81

^a Control: spore germination recorded at 15 hours (70%) and colony diameter after 10 days of incubation (3.5 cm).